

Together,
there's
something
science
can do.

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[US FDA launches AI tool to reduce time taken for scientific reviews](#): The FDA launched a new generative AI tool, Elsa, on June 2 to help expedite the processing time for scientific reviews of new drug applications. [According to the FDA](#), Elsa is designed to assist with tasks that involve reading, writing, and summarizing. [It is unclear](#) if the FDA will disclose how AI will be used to come to decisions, or how much the FDA will audit Elsa's output. Elsa also cannot yet access newly published information, [raising questions](#) about the tool's readiness for use.

[RFK Jr. names vaccine skeptics after firing previous advisory committee](#): US Health Secretary Robert F. Kennedy Jr. removed all 17 sitting members of the CDC's Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices (ACIP), replacing them with eight people who share anti-vaccine views. While Kennedy claimed the change was necessary to eliminate conflicts of interest and to restore public confidence in vaccine science, his choices have a record of having [criticized](#) the authorization of life-saving COVID vaccines. The American Medical Association called on the Senate to investigate the panel's dismissal.

[Eli Lilly and Juvena enter into \\$650M agreement to find muscle-boosting drugs](#): Eli Lilly is partnering with Juvena Therapeutics to identify drugs that improve muscle health and body composition. The partnership includes more than \$650 million in milestone incentives. Lilly believes it can leverage Juvena's AI-enabled screening platform to identify molecules which preserve lean muscle mass. Demand for this type of drug has skyrocketed in response to the widespread use of GLP-1 medications, which causes people to lose lean mass.

[Big Ten Academic Alliance and Springer Nature enter into Open Access Publishing Agreement](#): Springer Nature signed an open publishing agreement with the Big Ten Academic Alliance, its first ever in the Americas. This partnership between Springer and fourteen universities allows academic authors to publish their work in all Springer hybrid journals without paying article processing charges. It also makes their work immediately accessible at no cost under a Creative Commons license. As part of the deal, the participating universities get full read access to all Springer publications.